

closer affinity to the *O. glaberrima*-*O. barthii* group than to the Asian *O. rufipogon* group, although it had been considered a subtype of *O. rufipogon*.

The Asian group comprised four or five loosely knit groups, each corresponding to the indica type (including some *O. rufipogon*), japonica type (including *O. rufipogon* from China), *O. rufipogon* (consisting of several subgroups), and *O. nivara* (see figure). Some *O. rufipogon*-*O. nivara* showed close affinity to cultivated rice, as suggested by previous studies (Wang et al 1992, Nakano et al 1992).

Three accessions of perennial *O. rufipogon* from Papua New Guinea (excluded from the figure) carried both fragments of *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis*. Although no *O. meridionalis* has been reported from Papua New Guinea so far, it is possible that some exist in the country and that the natural hybrids between *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis* could have survived until now.

The classification among species matched well with the findings of previous studies (Morishima 1969, Second 1985, Wang et al 1992). Further analysis is needed to reveal the relationships among Asian subgroups.

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Detection of D genome chromosomes by genomic in situ hybridization

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Based on chromosome pairing at meiosis, it is known that the genus *Oryza* has five genomes (A, B, C, E, and F) in the diploid species. Tetraploid species with BC or CD genomes have also been found, although a diploid species with the D genome has not yet been discovered. The D genome is only found in tetraploids (*O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, and *O. latifolia* from Central and South America) in combination with the C genome.

In this study, we visualized D genome chromosomes on a glass slide in a CD genome tetraploid species. We used a chromosome painting method in which we applied the genomic in situ hybridization (GISH) method, using the total genomic DNA isolated from a C genome diploid species, *O. officinalis* (2n=24), labeled with biotin as the probe. *O. latifolia* was used to prepare chromosomes.

Chromosome samples were prepared by an enzymatic macerated/air drying method. The chromosome samples were treated with an enzymatic mixture (2% cellulase onozuka RS, 1.5% macerozyme R-200, 0.3% Pectolyase Y-23), proteinase K (1 mg ml⁻¹), 4.5% acetic acid, and RNase A (1 mg ml⁻¹) prior to in situ hybridization to get clear genome-specific fluorescent signals on small chromosomes.

The post-treatment removed cytoplasmic debris, cellular protein, and RNAs that cause nonspecific signals. In addition, a modified thermal cycler with a flat aluminum plate was developed and used to precisely control temperature. The results of GISH were analyzed using CHIAS 2, an image-analyzing system that provides clear fluorescent signal reproduction. This system can capture the fluorescent signals of GISH within a second, enhance weak signals, and even superimpose the signal images onto the original chromosome

We identified 24 C genome chromosomes, detected by the fluorescent probe of *O. officinalis*, from a mixture of 48 *O. latifolia* chromosomes belonging to the C and D genomes. All 24 D genome chromosomes were clearly identified using the imaging method, as were 24 C genome chromosomes from the 48 chromosomes with B and C genomes.

We also found differences in the relative strength of fluorescent signals between C and D genomes, and between B and C genomes. The differences in the fluorescent signal strength between B and C genome chromosomes were more distinct than those between C and D genome chromosomes, despite applying the same probe. These differences reflect the sequence homology between the C and D or B genomes. The D genome is considered to be more similar to the C genome than to the B genome.

We will continue to use the GISH method to provide new information about the relationships among the six genomes in *Oryza*. ■

Fingerprinting rice germplasm using ALP and PCR-based RFLP

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Morphological and isozyme markers provide a simple method for classifying rice collections. However, the markers available and their level of polymorphism are inconveniently low. DNA markers, on the

other hand, are abundant, high in their level of polymorphism, and known to be useful for germplasm surveys.

We evaluated the usefulness of converting mapped restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers to polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based markers, such as amplicon length polymorphism (ALP), and PCR-based RFLP (Ghareyazie et al 1995). This is the first report on applying ALP and or PCR to classify rice and on classifying Iranian rice varieties at the DNA level.